

Recovering metals and mineral fraction
from steelmaking residues

Deliverable

Description of ReMFra Key Performance Indicators and
other impacts D6.1

	Name	Signature and Date
Prepared by:	Wolfgang Reiter	
Checked by:	Johannes Rieger	
Approved by:	Manuel Mosconi	

Project details

Project Title	Recovering metals and mineral fractions from steelmaking residues		
Project Acronym	ReMFra		
Grant Agreement No.	101058362	Duration	42 months
Project Start Date	01.12.2022	Project End Date	30.05.2026

Document details

WP:	6	WP Leader:	FeHS
WP Title:	Key Performance Indicators and process certification		
Task:	6.1	Task Leader:	K1-MET
Task Title:	Definition and evaluation of Key Performance Indicators		
Deliverable No.	6.1		
Deliverable Title	Description of Key Performance Indicators and other Impacts		
Dissemination level	Public		
Written By	Wolfgang Reiter		
Contributing beneficiary(ies)	K1-MET, MUL, DALMINE, TENOVA		
Approved by	DALMINE		
Status	Version 1.0		
Date	31.03.2023		

Document history

Vers	DATE	AUTHOR / REVIEWER	NOTES
0.1		Reiter	Preparation of initial version
0.2			
1.0		Mosconi	Final draft
1.1			
1.2			
2.0			
2.1			

Table of Content

Abstract	7
1 Introduction.....	8
2 Key Performance Indicators.....	10
2.1 General description of a KPI according to ISO 22400	10
2.2 Table structure of a KPI.....	10
3 Defined Key Performance Indicators of the ReMFra process	11
3.1 Yield related Key Performance Indicators.....	11
3.1.1 <i>Specific product recovery efficiency overall (r_{pe})</i>	11
3.1.2 <i>Specific metal recovery efficiency Plasma ($r_{mFe,1}$)</i>	12
3.1.3 <i>Ferrous content of the Plasma slag ($r_{mFe,2}$)</i>	14
3.1.4 <i>Specific iron recovery efficiency RecoDust (r_{RDSFe})</i>	15
3.1.5 <i>Specific zinc recovery efficiency (r_{Zn})</i>	16
3.1.6 <i>Specific mineral recovery efficiency Plasma (r_{min})</i>	17
3.2 Energy related Key Performance Indicators	18
3.2.1 <i>Specific electrical energy Plasma (e_{es})</i>	18
3.2.2 <i>Specific reducing agent energy Plasma ($e_{ras,1}$)</i>	19
3.2.3 <i>Specific reducing agent energy RecoDust ($e_{ras,2}$)</i>	20
3.2.4 <i>Specific energy recovery rate (e_{rr})</i>	21
3.2.5 <i>Specific energy recovery rate Plasma ($e_{rr, p}$)</i>	22
3.2.6 <i>Specific energy recovery rate RecoDust (err, RD)</i>	23
3.3 Global warming related Key Performance Indicators.....	24
3.3.1 <i>Specific process CO₂ emissions ($CO_{2specific}$)</i>	24
3.3.2 <i>Specific Plasma reactor CO₂ emissions</i>	25
3.3.3 <i>Specific RecoDust CO₂ emissions</i>	26
3.4 Cost related Key Performance Indicators	26
3.4.1 <i>Specific energy costs (e_{sc})</i>	27

3.4.2	<i>Specific energy costs Plasma</i>	27
3.4.3	<i>Specific energy costs RecoDust</i>	29
3.4.4	<i>Specific ReMFra plant costs</i>	30
4	Target values of some Key Performance Indicators	31
5	References	32

List of Tables

Table 1:	Table structure of a KPI consisting of a content and a context information.....	10
Table 2:	Description of the KPI "Specific product recovery efficiency overall (r_{pe})"	12
Table 3:	Description of the KPI "specific metal recovery efficiency($r_{mFe,1}$)"	13
Table 4:	Description of the KPI "specific metal recovery efficiency($r_{mFe,2}$)"	14
Table 5:	Description of the KPI "Specific iron recovery efficiency RecoDust (r_{RDSFe})"	15
Table 6:	Description of the KPI "Specific zinc recovery efficiency (r_{Zn})"	16
Table 7:	Description of the KPI "Specific mineral recovery efficiency Plasma (r_{min})"	17
Table 8:	Description of the KPI "Specific electrical energy Plasma (e_{es})"	18
Table 9:	Description of the KPI "Specific reducing agent energy Plasma (e_{ras})"	19
Table 10:	Description of the KPI "Specific reducing agent energy RecoDust (e_{ras})"	20
Table 11:	Description of the KPI "Specific energy recovery rate (e_{rr})"	21
Table 12:	Description of the KPI "Specific energy recovery rate Plasma ($e_{rr,P}$)"	22
Table 13:	Description of the KPI "Specific energy recovery rate RecoDust ($e_{rr,RD}$)"	23
Table 14:	Description of the KPI "Specific process CO ₂ emissions ($CO_{2specific}$)"	24
Table 15:	Description of the KPI "Specific CO ₂ emissions of the Plasma reactor (CO_{2sP})"	25
Table 16:	Description of the KPI "Specific CO ₂ emissions of the RecoDust process"	26
Table 17:	Description of the KPI "Specific energy costs (e_{sc})"	27
Table 18:	Description of KPI EC-02 "Specific energy costs Plasma (e_{scP})"	28
Table 19:	Description of the KPI EC-03 "Specific energy costs RecoDust ($e_{sc,RD}$)"	29
Table 20:	Description of the KPI EC-04 "Specific ReMFra plant costs (e_{RPC})"	30
Table 21:	Target values of KPI's of the ReMFra project.....	31

List of Figures

Figure 1: ReMFra concept for the improvement of the yield of the iron and steel making in blue, optional stream in red, embracing the business [1] 8

Abbreviations and acronyms

RDS	RecoDust slag
CZO	Crude zinx oxide
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
CSP	Clean steel Partnership

Abstract

This deliverable is developed in the work package 6 “Key Performance Indicators and process certification“ of the Project 101058362 — ReMFra.

This deliverable 6.1 represents the defined Key Performance Indicator (KPI) for the ReMFra process according to ISO22400.

The Key Performance Indicators are categorized as following:

- Yield related Indicators.
- Global Warming related Indicators.
- Energy related Indicators.
- Economy related Indicators.

Every Key Performance Indicator is described in a table structure with a content and a context information. The selected Key Performance Indicators are intended to evaluate the ReMFra process in terms of resource efficiency, specific energy demand, specific greenhouse gas emissions and specific costs.

1 Introduction

The deliverable 6.1 is done in the Work Package 6 Key Performance Indicators and process certification. The main objectives of this Work Package are to define and evaluate the Key Performance Indicators, assess the ReMFra products quality, and certificate the new ReMFra process and products. [1]

In this deliverable the Key Performance Indicators are described regarding to the ISO22400 “Automation systems and integrations – Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for manufacturing operation management”.

The Key Performance Indicators are categorized as following:

- Yield related indicator.
- Global Warming related Indicators.
- Energy related Indicators.
- Economy related Indicators.

The ReMFra concept is shown in Figure 1 and consists of a Plasma reactor for the treatment of coarse residues and the RecoDust process for the treatment of dusty residues. Some KPIs are defined for the Plasma reactor, some for the RecoDust process and some for the ReMFra process.

Figure 1: ReMFra concept for the improvement of the yield of the iron and steel making in blue, optional stream in red, embracing the business [1]

Furthermore, the KPIs are in line with the targets and objectives of the clean steel partnership and some target values of the KPI's are mentioned. [2]

2 Key Performance Indicators

The Key Performance Indicators are compiled and defined regarding to ISO22400. [3]

2.1 General description of a KPI according to ISO 22400

The ISO22400 “Automation systems and integrations – Key Performance Indicators (KPIs) for manufacturing operation management” is motivated by the possibility to use them to improve the value creation processes of an enterprise. A good KPI has to fulfil some criteria which are listed in the ISO22400, some examples are aligned, balanced, standardised, valid, trackable or comparable. [3]

2.2 Table structure of a KPI

The table structure of a KPI is shown in Table 1. A KPI is described by its content and its context information. In the content information there are some quantifiable elements with a specific unit of measure and in the context information there is a verifiable list of conditions that are met. [3]

Table 1: Table structure of a KPI consisting of a content and a context information

KPI description
Content:
Name
ID
Description
Scope
Formula
Unit of measure
Range
Trend
Context:
Timing
Audience
Production methodology
Effect model diagram
Notes

3 Defined Key Performance Indicators of the ReMFra process

In this chapter, the Key Performance Indicators for the ReMFra process are set and the dedicated targets are mentioned.

3.1 Yield related Key Performance Indicators

In this chapter the yield related KPI's are mentioned. These indicators are named according to the following nomenclature: Y-01, Y-02 and following.

3.1.1 Specific product recovery efficiency overall (r_{pe})

The description of the KPI with the ID Y-01 is shown in Table 2. In the ReMFra process, a specific product recovery efficiency overall of higher than 80 % is envisaged. This KPI Y-01 is dedicated to the ReMFra process, including the Plasma reactor and the RecoDust process. The products from the plasma reactor are the pig iron and the mineral fraction, the products of the RecoDust process are the RecoDust slag (RDS) and the crude zinc oxide (CZO).

Table 2: Description of the KPI "Specific product recovery efficiency overall (r_{pe})"

KPI description	
Content:	
Name	Specific product recovery efficiency overall (r_{pe})
ID	Y-01
Description	The ratio of the total recovered product mass ($m_{products}$) and the mass of feed steel making residues (m_{feed})
Scope	Yield related
Formula	$r_{pe} = \frac{m_{products}}{m_{feed}}$
Unit of measure	%
Range	Min: 0% Max: 100%
Trend	The higher, the better
Context:	
Timing	On-demand
Audience	operator, supervisor
Production methodology	batchwise
Effect model diagram	
Notes	ReMFra overall, the products of the Plasma Reactor are the pig iron and the mineral fraction. In case of the RecoDust process the products are the RecoDust slag and the crude zinc oxide.

3.1.2 Specific metal recovery efficiency Plasma ($r_{mFe,1}$)

The KPI Y-02 "Specific metal recovery efficiency ($r_{mFe,1}$)" is shown in Table 3. The envisaged $r_{mFe,1}$ should be higher than 90 wt.-%. The recovered iron is the main component of the pig iron.

Table 3: Description of the KPI “specific metal recovery efficiency($r_{mFe,1}$)”

KPI description	
Content:	
Name	Specific metal recovery efficiency ($r_{mFe,1}$)
ID	Y-02
Description	The ratio of the total recovered iron mass ($m_{\text{recovered Fe}}$) and the mass of iron feed ($m_{\text{feed Fe}}$)
Scope	Yield related
Formula	$r_{mFe} = \frac{m_{\text{recovered Fe}}}{m_{\text{feed Fe}}}$
Unit of measure	%
Range	Min: 0% Max: 100%
Trend	The higher, the better
Context:	
Timing	On-demand
Audience	operator, supervisor
Production methodology	batchwise
Effect model diagram	
Notes	Plasma – the recovered iron is the main component of the pig iron

3.1.3 Ferrous content of the Plasma slag ($r_{mFe,2}$)

The KPI “Ferrous content of the Plasma slag ($r_{mFe,2}$)” is shown in Table 4. The iron content of the Plasma slag should be as low as possible for a high iron recovery.

Table 4: Description of the KPI “specific metal recovery efficiency($r_{mFe,2}$)”

KPI description	
Content:	
Name	Ferrous content of the Plasma slag ($r_{mFe,2}$)
ID	Y-03
Description	Content of ferrous oxides present in the slag after Plasma Reactor
Scope	Yield related
Formula	$r_{mFe,2} = \% Fe \text{ in Plasma slag}$
Unit of measure	%
Range	Min: 0% Max: 100%
Trend	The lower, the better
Context:	
Timing	On-demand
Audience	operator, supervisor
Production methodology	batchwise
Effect model diagram	
Notes	Plasma

3.1.4 Specific iron recovery efficiency RecoDust (r_{RDSFe})

In Table 5 the KPI “Specific iron recovery efficiency RecoDust (r_{RDSFe})” of the RecoDust process is defined. The recovered iron in the RDS is normally bivalent or trivalent, the iron of the feed material can be metallic, bivalent, or trivalent. For the calculation the amount of total iron must be used and the target value is set with more than 85 % iron recovery.

Table 5: Description of the KPI “Specific iron recovery efficiency RecoDust (r_{RDSFe})”

KPI description	
Content:	
Name	Specific iron recovery efficiency RecoDust (r_{RDSFe})
ID	Y-04
Description	The ratio of the total recovered iron mass ($m_{Fe\ recovered\ RDS}$) and the mass of the iron feed ($m_{feed\ Fe}$) for the RecoDust process
Scope	Yield related
Formula	$r_{RDSFe} = \frac{m_{Fe\ recovered\ RDS}}{m_{feed\ Fe}}$
Unit of measure	%
Range	Min: 0% Max: 100%
Trend	The higher, the better
Context:	
Timing	On-demand
Audience	operator, supervisor
Production methodology	batchwise
Effect model diagram	
Notes	RecoDust

3.1.5 Specific zinc recovery efficiency (r_{Zn})

The KPI Y-05 “Specific zinc recovery efficiency (r_{Zn})” is shown in Table 6. The zinc recovery efficiency should be as high as possible and the target value is a zinc recovery efficiency of more than 95 %. In this consideration zinc can be recovered if it is not in the RDS.

Table 6: Description of the KPI “Specific zinc recovery efficiency (r_{Zn})”

KPI description	
Content:	
Name	Specific zinc recovery efficiency (r_{Zn})
ID	Y-05
Description	The ratio of the remaining zinc mass in the RDS ($m_{Zn\ RDS}$) and the mass of the zinc feed ($m_{Zn\ feed}$) for the RecoDust process.
Scope	Yield related
Formula	$r_{Zn} = \left(1 - \frac{m_{Zn\ RDS}}{m_{Zn\ feed}}\right)$
Unit of measure	%
Range	Min: 0% Max: 100%
Trend	The higher, the better
Context:	
Timing	On-demand
Audience	operator, supervisor
Production methodology	batchwise
Effect model diagram	
Notes	RecoDust

3.1.6 Specific mineral recovery efficiency Plasma (r_{min})

In Table 7 the KPI Y-06 “Specific mineral recovery efficiency Plasma (r_{min})” is shown and describes the ratio between the recovered mineral product mass and the mineral mass of feed stream.

Table 7: Description of the KPI “Specific mineral recovery efficiency Plasma (r_{min})”

KPI description	
Content:	
Name	Specific mineral recovery efficiency Plasma (r_{min})
ID	Y-06
Description	The ratio of the total recovered mineral product ($m_{mineral\ recovered}$) mass and the mineral mass of feed stream ($m_{feed\ mineral}$)
Scope	Yield related
Formula	$r_{min} = \frac{m_{mineral\ recovered}}{m_{feed\ mineral}}$
Unit of measure	%
Range	Min: 0% Max: 100%
Trend	The higher, the better
Context:	
Timing	On-demand
Audience	operator, supervisor
Production methodology	batchwise
Effect model diagram	
Notes	Plasma

3.2 Energy related Key Performance Indicators

In this chapter the yield related KPI's are mentioned. These indicators are named according to the following nomenclature: E-01, E-02 and following.

3.2.1 Specific electrical energy Plasma (e_{es})

In Table 8 the KPI E-01 "Specific electrical energy Plasma (e_{es})" is shown. The electrical energy is needed to melt the feedstock of the Plasma reactor, the mass of products are the pig iron and the mineral fraction.

Table 8: Description of the KPI "Specific electrical energy Plasma (e_{es})"

KPI description	
Content:	
Name	Specific electrical energy Plasma (e_{es})
ID	E-01
Description	The ratio of the electrical energy consumption ($E_{\text{electrical}}$) and the mass of recovered products (m_{products})
Scope	Energy related
Formula	$e_{es} = \frac{E_{\text{electrical}}}{m_{\text{products}}}$
Unit of measure	kWh/t
Range	Min: 0 Max: Infinite
Trend	The lower, the better
Context:	
Timing	On-demand
Audience	operator, supervisor
Production methodology	batchwise
Effect model diagram	
Notes	Plasma, the products are the pig iron and the mineral fraction.

3.2.2 Specific reducing agent energy Plasma ($e_{ras,1}$)

The KPI E-02 “Specific reducing agent energy Plasma ($e_{ras,1}$)” is shown in Table 9. The reducing energy is provided by the injection of coal or polymers and the products are the pig iron and the mineral fraction. It is important to state the reducing agent.

Table 9: Description of the KPI “Specific reducing agent energy Plasma (e_{ras})”

KPI description	
Content:	
Name	Specific reducing agent energy Plasma ($e_{ras,1}$)
ID	E-02
Description	The ratio of the reducing agent energy consumption ($E_{reducing\ agent}$) and the mass of recovered products ($m_{products}$)
Scope	Energy related
Formula	$e_{ras,1} = \frac{E_{reducing\ agent}}{m_{products}}$
Unit of measure	kWh/t
Range	Min: 0 Max: Infinite
Trend	The lower, the better
Context:	
Timing	On-demand
Audience	operator, supervisor
Production methodology	batchwise
Effect model diagram	
Notes	Plasma, the products are the pig iron and the mineral fraction. Several inputs could be used as reducing agent and therefore an “energy KPI” is considered, it is important to state the reducing agent when this KPI is involved.

3.2.3 Specific reducing agent energy RecoDust ($e_{ras,2}$)

The KPI E-03 “Specific reducing agent energy RecoDust ($e_{ras,2}$)” is shown in Table 10. The reducing agent energy is supplied by the natural gas and hydrogen and is strongly influenced by the selected air excess ratio. The products of the RecoDust process are the RDS and the CZO.

Table 10: Description of the KPI “Specific reducing agent energy RecoDust (e_{ras})”

KPI description	
Content:	
Name	Specific reducing agent energy RecoDust ($e_{ras,2}$)
ID	E-03
Description	The ratio of the reducing agent energy consumption ($E_{reducing\ agent}$) and the mass of recovered products ($m_{products}$)
Scope	Energy related
Formula	$e_{ras,2} = \frac{E_{reducing\ agent}}{m_{products}}$
Unit of measure	kWh/t
Range	Min: 0 Max: Infinite
Trend	The lower, the better
Context:	
Timing	On-demand
Audience	operator, supervisor
Production methodology	batchwise
Effect model diagram	
Notes	RecoDust, the products are the RecoDust slag and the crude zinc oxide. Several inputs could be used as reducing agent and therefore an “energy KPI” is considered, it is important to state the reducing agent when this KPI is involved.

3.2.4 Specific energy recovery rate (e_{rr})

The KPI E-04 “Specific energy recovery rate (e_{rr})” is calculated by the recovered energy divided by the used energy and is shown in Table 11. Energy can be recovered from liquid metal (Plasma), molten slag (Plasma and RecoDust) and the off gas. Due to limitation of the budget, the installation of these will not in frame of the ReMFra project but can be theoretical calculated and be addressed in synergic projects.

Table 11: Description of the KPI “Specific energy recovery rate (e_{rr})”

KPI description	
Content:	
Name	Specific energy recovery rate (e_{rr})
ID	E-04
Description	The ratio of the useable energy recovered ($E_{recovered}$) and the energy used (E_{used})
Scope	Energy related
Formula	$e_{rr} = \frac{E_{recovered}}{E_{used}}$
Unit of measure	%
Range	Min: 0% Max: 100%
Trend	The higher, the better
Context:	
Timing	On-demand
Audience	operator, supervisor
Production methodology	batchwise
Effect model diagram	
Notes	ReMFra overall, based on calculation (model simulation)

3.2.5 Specific energy recovery rate Plasma ($e_{rr,P}$)

In Table 12 the KPI “Specific energy recovery rate Plasma ($e_{rr,P}$)” is shown. The energy can be recovered from liquid metal, molten slag and the off gas. Due to limitation of the budget, the installation of these will not in frame of the ReMFra project but can be theoretical calculated and be addressed in synergic projects.

Table 12: Description of the KPI “Specific energy recovery rate Plasma ($e_{rr,P}$)”

KPI description	
Content:	
Name	Specific energy recovery rate Plasma ($e_{rr,P}$)
ID	E-05
Description	The ratio of the useable energy recovered ($E_{recovered}$) and the energy used (E_{used})
Scope	Energy related
Formula	$e_{rr,P} = \frac{E_{recovered}}{E_{used}}$
Unit of measure	%
Range	Min: 0% Max: 100%
Trend	The higher, the better
Context:	
Timing	On-demand
Audience	operator, supervisor
Production methodology	batchwise
Effect model diagram	
Notes	Plasma case Calculations made with model simulations

3.2.6 Specific energy recovery rate RecoDust ($e_{rr, RD}$)

In Table 13 the KPI “Specific energy recovery rate RecoDust ($e_{rr, RD}$)” is shown. The energy can be recovered from molten RecoDust slag and the off gas. Due to limitation of the budget, the installation of these will not in frame of the ReMFra project but can be theoretical calculated and be addressed in synergic projects.

Table 13: Description of the KPI “Specific energy recovery rate RecoDust ($e_{rr, RD}$)”

KPI description	
Content:	
Name	Specific energy recovery rate RecoDust ($e_{rr, RD}$)
ID	E-06
Description	The ratio of the useable energy recovered ($E_{recovered}$) and the energy used (E_{used})
Scope	Energy related
Formula	$e_{rr, RD} = \frac{E_{recovered}}{E_{used}}$
Unit of measure	%
Range	Min: 0% Max: 100%
Trend	The higher, the better
Context:	
Timing	On-demand
Audience	operator, supervisor
Production methodology	batchwise
Effect model diagram	
Notes	RecoDust case Calculations made with model simulations

3.3 Global warming related Key Performance Indicators

In this section the global warming related Key Performance Indicators are described and are designated as GW-01, GW-02 and following.

3.3.1 Specific process CO₂ emissions (CO_{2specific})

The KPI GW-01 “Specific process CO₂ emissions (CO_{2specific})” is shown in Table 14. The CO₂ emissions will include scope 1, scope 2 and scope 3.

Table 14: Description of the KPI “Specific process CO₂ emissions (CO_{2specific})”

KPI description	
Content:	
Name	Specific process CO₂ emissions (CO_{2specific})
ID	GW-01
Description	The ratio of the CO ₂ emissions per ton product produced
Scope	Global warming related
Formula	$CO_{2specific} = \frac{m_{CO_2 \text{ emissions}}}{m_{products}}$
Unit of measure	Kg, CO ₂ /kg, products
Range	Min: - Infinite Max: Infinite
Trend	The lower, the better
Context:	
Timing	On-demand
Audience	operator, supervisor
Production methodology	batchwise
Effect model diagram	
Notes	ReMFra overall This KPI will include scope 1, scope 2 and scope 3 (considering also the impacts on other value chain) and should be less than zero because of scope 3.

3.3.2 Specific Plasma reactor CO₂ emissions

Table 15 shows the KPI GW-02 “Specific process CO₂ emissions Plasma CO_{2sP}”. The CO₂ emissions SCOPE 1 in case of the plasma reactor comes from the reducing agent (coal or polymers) and the emissions from SCOPE 2 are linked to the purchase of electricity. The products are the pig iron and the mineral fraction.

Table 15: Description of the KPI “Specific CO₂ emissions of the Plasma reactor (CO_{2sP})”

KPI description	
Content:	
Name	Specific process CO₂ emissions Plasma (CO_{2sP})
ID	GW-02
Description	The ratio of the CO ₂ emissions per ton product produced
Scope	Global warming related
Formula	$CO_{2,specific,P} = \frac{m_{CO_2 \text{ emissions}}}{m_{products}}$
Unit of measure	Kg CO ₂ //kg, products
Range	Min: 0 Max: Infinite
Trend	The lower, the better
Context:	
Timing	On-demand
Audience	operator, supervisor
Production methodology	batchwise
Effect model diagram	
Notes	Plasma case This KPI will include scope 1 and scope 2 and will evaluate just the plasma process and not the impacts outside the process.

3.3.3 Specific RecoDust CO₂ emissions

The KPI GW-03 “Specific CO₂ emissions of the RecoDust process (CO_{2sRD})” is shown in Table 16. The CO₂ emissions SCOPE 1 in case of RecoDust originate from the reducing agent (natural gas) and the emissions from SCOPE 2 are linked to the purchase of electricity. The products are the RecoDust slag and the crude zinc oxide.

Table 16: Description of the KPI “Specific CO₂ emissions of the RecoDust process”

KPI description	
Content:	
Name	Specific process CO₂ emissions RecoDust (CO_{2sRD})
ID	GW-03
Description	The ratio of the CO ₂ emissions per ton product produced
Scope	Global warming related
Formula	$CO_{2specific, RD} = \frac{m_{CO_2 \text{ emissions}}}{m_{products}}$
Unit of measure	Kg, CO ₂ /kg, products
Range	Min: 0 Max: Infinite
Trend	The lower, the better
Context:	
Timing	On-demand
Audience	operator, supervisor
Production methodology	batchwise
Effect model diagram	
Notes	RecoDust This KPI will include scope 1 and scope 2 and will evaluate just the RecoDust process and not the impacts outside the process

3.4 Cost related Key Performance Indicators

In this section, the cost related Key Performance Indicators are subscribed including energy costs, and plant costs. The cost related indicators are named according to the following nomenclature: C-01, C-02 and following.

3.4.1 Specific energy costs (e_{sc})

The Key Performance Indicator C-01 “Specific energy costs (e_{sc})” is shown in Table 17. The energy costs are composed of costs for electrical and for reducing agent energy. The mass of the products is in case of the plasma reactor the pig iron and the mineral fraction and in case of the RecoDust process the RecoDust slag and the crude zinc oxide.

Table 17: Description of the KPI “Specific energy costs (e_{sc})”

KPI description	
Content:	
Name	Specific energy costs (e_{sc})
ID	C-01
Description	The ratio of the energy costs (C_E) and the mass of the products of the ReMFra process ($m_{products}$)
Scope	Cost related
Formula	$e_{sc} = \frac{C_e}{m_{products}}$
Unit of measure	€/t
Range	Min: 0 Max: Infinite
Trend	The lower, the better
Context:	
Timing	On-demand
Audience	Operator, supervisor
Production methodology	Batchwise
Effect model diagram	
Notes	ReMFra overall, the products of the Plasma Reactor are the pig iron and the mineral fraction. In case of the RecoDust process the products are the RecoDust slag and the crude zinc oxide.

3.4.2 Specific energy costs Plasma

The Key Performance Indicator C-02 “Specific energy costs Plasma(e_{scP})” is shown in Table 18 and describes the ratio of the energy costs of the plasma process and the costs for melting the same amount of scrap and the avoided costs for capture of the CO₂ during transport and melting the scrap.

Table 18: Description of KPI EC-02 "Specific energy costs Plasma (e_{scP})"

KPI description	
Content:	
Name	Specific energy costs Plasma ($e_{sc,P}$)
ID	C-02
Description	The ratio of the energy costs (C_E) and the mass of the products of the Plasma process ($m_{products}$)
Scope	Cost related
Formula	$e_{sc,P} = \frac{C_e}{m_{products}}$
Unit of measure	€/t
Range	Min: 0 Max: Infinite
Trend	The lower, the better
Context:	
Timing	On-demand
Audience	Operator, supervisor
Production methodology	Batchwise
Effect model diagram	
Notes	The products of the Plasma Reactor are the pig iron and the mineral fraction.

3.4.3 Specific energy costs RecoDust

The KPI C-03 “Specific energy costs RecoDust ($e_{sc, RD}$)” is shown in Table 19. The products of the RecoDust process are the RDS and the CZO.

Table 19: Description of the KPI EC-03 “Specific energy costs RecoDust ($e_{sc, RD}$)”

KPI description	
Content:	
Name	Specific energy costs RecoDust ($e_{sc, RD}$)
ID	C-03
Description	The ratio of the energy costs (C_E) and the mass of the products of the RecoDust process ($m_{products}$)
Scope	Cost related
Formula	$e_{sc, RD} = \frac{C_e}{m_{products}}$
Unit of measure	€/t
Range	Min: 0 Max: Infinite
Trend	The lower, the better
Context:	
Timing	On-demand
Audience	Operator, supervisor
Production methodology	Batchwise
Effect model diagram	
Notes	The products of the RecoDust process the products are the RecoDust slag and the crude zinc oxide.

3.4.4 Specific ReMFra plant costs

The KPI C-04 “Specific ReMFra plant costs (e_{RPC}) is shown in Table 20. This KPI is very useful for ReMFra plant customers.

Table 20: Description of the KPI EC-04 “Specific ReMFra plant costs (e_{RPC})”

KPI description	
Content:	
Name	Specific ReMFra plant costs (e_{RPC})
ID	C-04
Description	The ratio of the ReMFra plant cost and the mass of the products per year
Scope	Cost related
Formula	$e_{RPC} = \frac{C_{ReMFra\ plant}}{m_{products}}$
Unit of measure	€/tons per year
Range	Min:0 Max: Infinite
Trend	The lower, the better
Context:	
Timing	On-demand
Audience	Operator, supervisor
Production methodology	Batchwise
Effect model diagram	
Notes	

4 Target values of some Key Performance Indicators

In Table 21 the target values of some Key Performance Indicators are shown. They are in line with the clean steel partnership. By achieving these goals, the ReMFra process will be a highly efficient process for the recovery and the valorisation of steel making processing residues with a high metal recovery yield to reach the full circularity and to reduce the environmental impact of the steel sector all over Europe.

Table 21: Target values of KPI's of the ReMFra project

KPI	Target Value
Y-01	>80%
Y-02	>90%
Y-04	>85%
Y-05	>95%
Y-06	>90%
E-04	>40%

Additionally, similar KPIs will be defined to compare the performance (energy and global warming related) and economic parameters of ReMFra approach with state-of-the-art residue treatment solutions. As a direct CO₂ minimisation for the internal recycling of the metal fraction derived from residues is strongly required by this CSP call being addressed by ReMFra, a CO₂ calculation procedure will be defined by K1-MET with the support of the partners.

5 References

1. Grant Agreement-101058362-ReMFra
2. European Steel Technology Platform (2020) Clean Steel Partnership Roadmap.
<https://www.estep.eu/assets/Uploads/200715-CSP-Roadmap-version-public-consultation.pdf>.
Accessed 27 Feb 2023
3. International Organization for Standardization Automation systems and integration - Key performance indicators (KPIs) for manufacturing operations management: Part 1: Overview, concepts and terminology, 1st ed. 25.040.01(ISO 22400-1:2014(ISO22400-1)